

Technical Paper

Innovations Introduced with the
New GGS Questionnaire

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1. INTRODUCTION

Compared to the 2004 questionnaire, the new one contains three main innovative aspects:

- “A revamping of the social network module. The new social network module makes it possible to more clearly distinguish the support relationships between genders and generations. This is important to better understand why certain family members offer and receive support, whereas others do not.
- Better measures of how societal constraints and social policies influence the decisions that individuals make concerning family formation and retirement. This is important, as one of the main goals of the GGP is to be able to understand how people react to changes in policy environments.
- Inclusion of a personality module. This is important as personality can have an impact on how individuals behave across a wide range of life domains and can have a long-lasting influence on how individuals react to adversity in the lives” (Deliverable¹ D38: p. 29).

These revisions were made due to the findings from methodological reports on the analysis of GGP Wave 1 collected data within the FP7 Design Study (D9, D11, D12, D13, D14, D21, D22, D23, D24). They were tested, both in CAPI and CAWI mode, in a pilot survey run in Slovenia in 2011 on 621 respondents (D18, D25).

For a comparative survey, cross-national equivalence – that instruments measure the same concept equivalently in different countries – is of utmost importance, and that equivalence was judged to be excellent for the large majority of the GGP measurement instruments (D38). For those instruments for which cross-national equivalence was evaluated to be subpar, alternative instruments were developed, and tested in the pilot survey. The tests were conducted as split-ballot experiments: one group was administered the original item wording in GGS wave 1, and the other group got the renewed wording of the same item.

In the following section, we summarize the main revisions introduced compared to GGS 2004 Core questionnaire², based on the methodological recommendations of some of the above mentioned reports. In Appendix, we further detail and explain these revisions. Throughout the text, we refer to the new GGS questionnaire version 2.7 (available in the Annex; a previous version of the new questionnaire was published in D26).

¹ See section 3 for deliverable titles and authors. Thereafter in the text, we abbreviate “Deliverable” with “D”.

² Available online: www.ggp-i.org/data/methodology; also published in UNECE - UNITED NATIONS ECONOMIC COMMISSION FOR EUROPE (2005) *Generations and Gender Programme - Survey Instruments*. New York/ Geneva: United Nations (available online: http://www.unece.org/pau/pub/ggp_survey_instruments.html).

2. MAIN METHODOLOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS AND CORRESPONDING QUESTIONNAIRE REVISIONS

First recommendation (D22)

To group the questions on providing and receiving help with a view to: a) achieving an increased focus on dependencies between generations and gender and comparability with other surveys (e.g., SHARE); b) reducing the questionnaire length, respondents' burden and the reliance on visual cues and tools for a possible administration via CATI and WEB.

Main corresponding questionnaire revisions

A new module entitled "Network delineation and support" (Q 5.01-5.41 of the new questionnaire) is introduced by grouping the previous sub-modules on childcare, household organisation, personal care, and monetary transfers and inheritance.

This grouping does not concern the questions on the repartition of tasks between partners which did not move, and allows for a significant simplification and reduction of the questionnaire flow. Additionally, it gives room for naming respondents' providers and for collecting their demographics, which increases dramatically the questionnaire quality for social network analyses.

Second recommendation (D13, D24)

To enhance the health and well-being module for a greater understanding of the role played by health status and personality traits in demographic behaviours.

Main corresponding questionnaire revisions

A set of new questions were introduced to capture respondents' satisfaction and happiness in life, their sense of control, their personality traits, and their objective health status (Q 7.01, 7.03-7.10 of the new questionnaire).

These revisions improve the quality of information on respondents' health, well-being and personality traits and allow for better considering these variables as potential causes and moderating factors of demographic behaviours. Additionally, they ameliorate the overall questionnaire cross-country comparability, as for example domain-specific items of the 2004 questions about satisfaction in life and locus of control were not applied in all countries.

Third recommendation (D23)

To account for indications from applied research in the life course and decision-making module, especially in the Theory of Planned Behaviour items.

Main corresponding questionnaire revisions

- a) Intention scale: a fifth mid-item "unsure" is introduced in all the questions asking about respondents' intention to undertake a given behaviour. The response categories become: "definitely not", "probably not", "unsure", "probably yes", "definitely yes".

This revision takes into account the findings of qualitative research within the European funded project REPRO (Reproductive decision-making) that “unsure” is a valid response to intention questions. Additionally, it dramatically increases the response rates for these questions without drastically changing the scale. Indeed, the pilot study in Slovenia showed that the distribution of answers for the remaining categories was not affected by the addition of the new item.

- b) Attitudes linked to intentions, questions (Q 2.80, 4.55, 6.18, 8.36 of the new questionnaire) formulated as:

Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to [behaviour]. I would like you to tell me what affect this would have on various aspects of your life. Please choose your answers...

A smaller and more harmonised list of behavioural beliefs is implemented and new questions on attitudes towards marriages are added (Q 2.84-2.86 of the new questionnaire) to better study this phenomenon. The list of behavioural beliefs become: “the possibility to do what you want”, “the amount of money you can spend”, “the possibility to realize other goals in life”, “the joy and satisfaction you get from life”. The item “my sexual life” is also included for attitudes towards living home; the items “your employment opportunities” and “your partner’s employment opportunities” for attitudes towards having a/another child; the item “spending time with your family” for attitudes towards retirement.

These revisions drastically simplify the old questionnaire where a total of 14 different behavioural beliefs were included. The old list of behavioural beliefs did not prove to be useful for applied research, especially for cross-country comparisons.

- c) Subjective norms, questions (Q 2.82, 2.86, 4.57, 6.20, 8.38 of the new questionnaire) formulated as follows:

Now I am going to read out some statements about what other people might think about you [behaviour] during the next 3 years. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements...

A common core of 3 items is used and reads as follows: “most of my friends think that I should...”, “my partner thinks that I should...”, “my parents think that I should...”. Additionally, these items are asked only if applicable (e.g., no question on partner’s opinions for those having no partner).

These revisions contribute to the simplification of the questionnaire.

- d) Perceived behavioural control, questions (Q 2.81, 2.85, 4.56, 6.19, 8.37 of the new questionnaire) formulated as follows:

I’m going to read out some statements about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before [behaviour]. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements....

The response categories are reframed and harmonized across the questions and adapted to an agreement scale. The 2004 items and scale (“not at all”, “a little”, “quite a lot”, “a great deal”) turned out to be not satisfying and of difficult usability for applied research.

The above mentioned revisions are guided by a common set of principles:

- greater relevance and comparability to the given behaviour/decision across countries and questions,
- greater conceptual adherence to the Theory of Planned Behaviour,
- asymmetry across domains and internal questionnaire consistency,
- effective feasibility in each country and continuity with the 2004 questionnaire.

Fourth recommendation (D21)

To simplify the module on economic well-being for a greater cross-country comparability, usefulness and usability in applied research.

Main corresponding questionnaire revisions

A significant number of questions are dropped because considered underused in research given their difficult interpretation. Keeping them does not justify the burden on respondents. Some other questions are re-framed, so as to account for greater cross-national comparability and harmonization with other international surveys (in particular with EU-SILC, which is the key source on living conditions in Europe).

a) Sub-module on education

The following questions of the 2004 Core questionnaire are dropped: questions on subject matters of study (old Q 121) and on intention to resume education within the next three years (old Q 124). This is done because countries operate with different groupings of subject matters of study which are difficult to compare, and the intention to resume education is of difficult interpretation as may depend on the attained level of education. The question on whether the respondent is currently studying is revised (Q 1.09 of the new questionnaire) adding the time frame “over the last 12 months” for greater comparability.

b) Sub-module on dwelling unit

Questions on intention to move (old Q 118 and 119) are dropped because underused.

c) Sub-module on child alimony/maintenance and partner alimony

Only some questions are maintained (Q 2.87-2.90 of the new questionnaire) that encapsulate all the necessary information in research and received the highest response rates in the majority of countries.

d) Respondent’s and partner’s activity and income

Main questions of the 2004 Core questionnaire that are dropped include:

- questions on satisfaction about current activity status (old Q 804, 809, 813),
- questions on intention to start working and complete education (old Q 810, 814, 820, and 826),

- questions on whether the leave is part-time or full-time (old Q 805b and 904b),
- questions on the description of working place and gender composition of work (old Q 836, 924, and 841),
- questions on regularity of the job and intention to change job (old Q 846, 848, 849),
- questions on satisfaction with being self-employed, on the expected future development of respondent's business/farm and on the intention to change job or stop paid work (old Q 850, 852, 853, 854),
- questions on the type of additional job/business (old Q 861, 863, 933, 935).

For example, the question on satisfaction on maternity/parental/childcare leave is dropped because it could refer to either the duration or the payment of the leave. Similarly, asking about the intention of finding a job could be interpreted as respondent's perceived likelihood of finding a job. Asking whether people are on part-time or full-time leave is not necessary because most people on part-time leave would qualify their status as being in work.

Main questions that are revised include:

- the question on the opportunity to resume work after leave that has a new response category "did not work prior to this leave" (Q 8.15, 9.12 of the new questionnaire),
- the question on job security (Q 8.31 of the new questionnaire) now focusing on the perceived (and not actual) situation,
- the questions on occupation (Q 8.07, 8.17, 9.04, 9.14 of the new questionnaire) that now are answered according to the ISCO-2008 code,
- the questions on work schedule (Q 8.20-8.24, 9.17-9.21 of the new questionnaire) now more comparable with other surveys.

e) Household possessions, income and transfers

Questions that are dropped include, e.g., those on items that the household possesses, on the capacity to save money and on whether other individuals in the household receive income. This increases the comparability with EU-SILC questions. Additionally, the questions on monetary transfers and inheritance are moved into the social network module, thus ameliorating the questionnaire flow.

Other questionnaire innovations

Household composition, organisation and partnership quality

To enhance the questionnaire flow, this module now includes the household roster sub-module and the one about division of childcare tasks among household members.

Partnership quality and household organization

To achieve greater equivalence across countries, the list of disagreement items and of household tasks are partially revised (Q 2.18, 2.19 and 3.11 of the new questionnaire).

Fecundity

Questions on fertility intentions in the 2004 Core questionnaire (old Q 611 and 615) are removed.

3. DELIVERABLES

- D9. Deliverable 9: Report on existing GGS measures on Life Course and Decision Making. By Jane Klobas, Silvia Ruggeri, Marta Marzi. December 2010.
- D11. Deliverable 11: Interviewer effects on survey non-response in the GGP. The Dutch experience. By Edith D. de Leeuw, Joop J. Hox, Suzette Mathijssse. January 2011.
- D12. Deliverable 12: Report on the substantive and methodological evaluation of the various social network indices in the Generations and Gender Survey. By Pearl A. Dykstra, Christoph Bühler, Tina Kogovšek, Valentina Hlebec, Tineke Fokkema. December 2010.
- D13. Deliverable 13: Report on evaluation of existing and feasibility for development of new psychological instruments in the GGS. By Julia Ratikainen, Thomas Hansen & Britt Slagsvold. December 2010.
- D14. Deliverable 14: Genetics and biomarkers in surveys. By John Hobcraft. December 2010.
- D18. Deliverable 18: Pilot study fieldwork documentation. By Gregor Petrič, Nejc Berzelak, Rok Platinovšek. December 2011.
- D21. Deliverable 21: Proposed new questionnaire module on economic well-being. By Arnstein Aassve, Ariane Pailhé, and Olivier Thévenon. January 2011.
- D22. Deliverable 22: Proposed new questionnaire module on social support networks. By Pearl Dykstra, Tina Kogovšek, Valentina Hlebec, Gregor Petrič, Christoph Bühler and Tineke Fokkema. January 2011.
- D23. Deliverable 23: Proposed new questionnaire module on life course and decision making. By Jane Klobas, Aart C. Liefbroer, Francesco C. Billari and Icek Ajzen. January 2012.
- D24. Deliverable 24: Proposed new questionnaire module on psychological instruments. By Britt Slagsvold and Thomas Hansen. March 2012.
- D25. Deliverable 25: Report on the study fieldwork experience, methodological experiments and functionality of newly developed instruments. By Gregor Petrič, Katja Lozar Manfreda and Rok Platinovšek. December 2012.
- D26. Finalized new GGS questionnaire. By Arnstein Aassve, Icek Ajzen, Francesco Billari, Christoph Bühler, Pearl Dykstra, Tineke Fokkema, Thomas Hansen, Valentina Hlebec, Jane Klobas, Tina Kogovšek, Andrej Kveder, Trude Lappegård, Aat Liefbroer, Lívia Murinkó, Ariane Pailhé, Gregor Petrič, Julia Ratikainen, Britt Slagsvold, Zsolt Spéder, Olivier Thévenon. June 2013.
- D38. Deliverable 38: Conceptual design report on the new infrastructure. January 2014.

APPENDIX – Revisions of the GGS questionnaire, compared to the 2004 one, by (sub-) modules and questions, and their reasons.

New questionnaire	2004 Questionnaire	Revisions	Reasons
Sub-module on education	Q 121 on subject matter of studies; Q 123 on whether R is currently studying; Q 124 on intention to resume education	Q 121 and 124 are dropped. Q 123 is revised (Q 1.09) adding the time frame “over the last 12 months”.	Q 124 was difficult to interpret in the sense that reported intention would depend directly on the stage of education one is enrolled in. Q 121 was not comparable across countries. Countries operate with different groupings that cannot be easily compared. Q 123 was revised for greater comparability.
Sub-module on dwelling unit	Q 118 and Q 119 on intentions to move	These questions are dropped.	These questions turned out to be useless for research questions.
Sub-modules on child Alimony/ maintenance and partner Alimony	Questions 338-353	Only question Q 339, Q 343, Q 347 and Q 351 from old questionnaire are kept (Q 2.87-2.90).	The dropped questions performed particularly badly as the number of valid responses was very low. The questions kept encapsulate the information of all the questions that were dropped.
Household composition, organization and partnership quality	Sub-modules on household roster and childcare	Questions on household, previously spread over the questionnaire are now grouped in a unique module.	This revision aims to increase the questionnaire flow.
Sub-modules on partnership quality and household organization	Q 401 and 408 on partnership disagreement, and 409 on division of household tasks between partners	Partially revised list of items (Q 2.18, 2.19, 3.11).	This revision aims to achieve greater comparability and equivalence across countries.

New questionnaire	2004 Questionnaire	Revisions	Reasons
Social network module	Sub-modules on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - childcare (Q 201-208); - household organization (Q 401-404); - personal care (Q 704-718); - monetary transfers and inheritance (Q 1010-1018) 	Questions on providing/receiving help are now grouped in a new module (Q 5.01-5.38); some of them are dropped or reformulated. This does not concern the division of tasks between partners. Additionally, the respondents are asked the characteristics (i.e., sex, age; type of relation) of their network members at the end of this module (Q 5.39-5.41).	These revisions aim to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduce interview length and time (20%) and respondents' burden; - increase the focus on dependencies between generations and genders; - achieve greater comparability with other surveys (e.g., SHARE); - reduce the reliance on visual cues and tools for a possible administration via CATI or WEB.
Sub-module on fecundity	Q 611 and Q 615 on intention to have children now	These questions are dropped.	All the questions on intentions to have children are placed in the dedicated sub-module.
Health and well-being module	Satisfaction in life was asked with reference to specific domains (Q 719). The other questions were absent.	New questions are introduced: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General satisfaction and happiness in life and global sense of control (Q 7.01, Q 7.09 and Q 7.10). - Personality traits (Q 7.08). - Health in general (Q 7.03-7.07). 	These revisions aim to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase the comparability as domain-specific items of locus of control were not applied in all countries; - increase the understanding of demographic behaviours as recent research showed that personality traits and global sense of control and well-being can be key causes and moderating factors of them; - better study respondents' health and greater comparability with other surveys.

New questionnaire	2004 Questionnaire	Revisions	Reasons	
Life course and decision making module (items of the Theory of Planned Behaviour)	Attitudes linked to intentions: 14 different behavioural beliefs were present (Q 320, 579, 627, 857)	New questions Q 2.84-2.86 about the decision to marry are introduced. A smaller “core” list of items is now used for all decisions (Q 2.80, 2.84, 4.55, 6.18, 8.36): “the possibility to do what you want”, “your financial situation”, “the possibility to realize other important goals in life”, “the joy and satisfaction you get from life”; plus specific items are used for specific decisions (e.g., “my sexual life” for leaving home)	The new question about attitudes towards marriage aims to better study this phenomenon. The general principles justifying all these revisions are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - greater relevance and compatibility to the behaviour/decision of interest across countries and sub-samples; - greater emphasis on generations and gender; - greater conceptual validity (i.e. reflection of the concepts as defined in the Theory of Planned Behaviour); - greater comparability across questions within the questionnaire; 	
	Subjective norms (Q 323, 582, 629, 859)	Q 2.82, 2.86, 4.57, 6.20, 8.38: a common core of 3 items are now used (“my partner”, “my parents”, “my friends”), plus “my employer” and “my children” for questions on retirement) and asked only if applicable.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - preservation of relevance, compatibility and conceptual validity; - asymmetry across domains, sufficiently and internal consistency; - feasibility in each country and continuity with the 2004 questionnaire.
	Perceived behavioural control (Q 321, 580, 628, 858) used the scale “not at all”, “a little”, “quite a lot”, “a great deal”.	The items were reframed, harmonized across the questions, and adapted to an agreement scale (Q 2.81, 2.85, 4.56, 6.19, 8.37).		

New questionnaire	2004 Questionnaire	Revisions	Reasons
Life course and decision making module (items of the Theory of Planned Behaviour) (continued)	Intention scale structured in 4-points: “definitely not”, “probably not”, “probably yes”, “definitely yes”.	A 5 th mid-point “unsure” is now available. The tests showed no scale effect on the distribution of answers: introducing the category “unsure” may draw respondents to this category without affecting the distribution of answers for the remaining categories.	The revision of the intention scale aim to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - give the opportunity to answer “unsure” which is a valid response to intention, as shown by qualitative research within the project REPRO; - increase the response rates for these questions; - provide for greater variance in answers, without drastically changing the scale; - allow for higher predictability of the intentions.
Respondent’s and partner’s activity and income modules	Q 804 on satisfaction of maternity/parental or childcare leave, and Q 805b and 904b on whether the leave is part-time or full-time	These questions are dropped.	This revision reduces the length of the questionnaire. As to Q 804 it was unclear whether the satisfaction was to be related to the payment or to the duration. As to Q 805b and 904b, in case of part-time work, people would qualify this status as being in work, plus in some countries people would work part-time even if they are on full leave. Instead of asking this, it is better to just ask only about part-time work.
	Q 806 and 905 on opportunity to resume work after leave	The category “did not work before leave” is added (Q 8.15 and 9.12)	This revision is introduced because in some countries people would answer that they/their partners are on maternity leave despite not having worked prior to it.
	Q 809 on satisfaction about being unemployed and Q 810 on intention to start working	These questions are dropped.	As to Q 809, most respondents were rather unsatisfied with being unemployed. As to Q 810, it was not clear whether the question reflected real intentions or rather the perceived likelihood of finding a job.

New questionnaire	2004 Questionnaire	Revisions	Reasons
Respondent's and partner's activity and income modules (continued)	Q 813 on satisfaction of being a student, and 814 on intention to complete education	These questions are dropped.	Q 813 and 814 are dropped because of difficult interpretation in applied research. The answer would be driven by the stage of education the respondent is enrolled in.
	Q 820 and 826 on intention to start working for permanently disabled and those in military or social service	These questions are dropped.	Q 820 and 827 are dropped because they concerned only very few people.
	Q 828, 832, 861, 917, 921, 933 on the type of occupation	ISCO-2008 codes instead of 1988 ones are now applied (Q 8.07, 8.17, 9.04, 9.14)	Update the questionnaire and increase comparability with other surveys.
	Q 837 and 925 on work schedule	These questions are revised and new ones are added (8.20-8.24; 9.17-9.21).	The aim is to make these questions more comparable with the same type of questions in other surveys.
	Q 841 on gender composition of work	The question is dropped.	A proxy to this question can be the question on type of occupation by ISCO codes.
	Q 847 on satisfaction about job security	This question is revised (Q 8.31).	This revision aims to focus on the perceived (and not actual) job security.
	Q 861, 863, 933 and 935 on the type of additional job/business; Q 836 and 924 on the description of work place; Q 846, 848, 849 on regularity of job and intention to change job	These questions are dropped.	These questions did not turn to be useful for research.
	Q 850 and Q 853-854 on satisfaction about self-employment and intention to change/stop job; Q 852 on the development of own business/farm	These questions are dropped.	These questions can be replaced by the extent to which respondent feels secure about his/her job.

New questionnaire	2004 Questionnaire	Revisions	Reasons
Household possessions, income and transfers module	Q 1001 on items that the household possesses; Q 1005 on capacity to save money; Q 1006 and 1007 on whether others in the household has income from other sources	These questions are dropped.	These revisions aim to achieve greater comparability with EU-SILC which is the key source of information for living standards in Europe and reduced length of the questionnaire. Information provided by Q 1005 was additional to Q 1002 (Q 10.04 of the new questionnaire).
	Module on monetary transfers and inheritance	This module is moved in the social network module (see above).	See above "Social network module".

ANNEX – The new Generations and Gender Survey questionnaire

Generations &
Gender Programme

Generations and Gender Survey Questionnaire

version. 2.7

*Arnstein Aassve, Icek Ajzen, Francesco Billari,
Christoph Bühler, Pearl Dykstra, Tineke Fokkema,
Thomas Hansen, Valentina Hlebec, Jane Klobas,
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**Den Haag
May 2015**

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Interviewer Instruction: Write in the time and date when the interview starts.

0.01. Interview started at _____ on _____

Interviewer Instruction: Read the following text.

This survey is called the Generations and Gender Survey. It is about topics related to children, partners, parents, work and everyday life. The aim is to study what factors influence family formation, having children, and relations between younger and older generations. The study is part of an international programme co-ordinated by the Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute and UN Economic Commission for Europe. Your participation is voluntary, but it is very important because you represent many other people. We will hold the information you give us in the strictest confidence and use it only for statistical processing. It would also be better if we could have this interview without others being present, if possible. If you have any questions, please let me know.

Interviewer Instruction: Write who else is present when the interview starts.

0.02. Other persons present at the start of interview

1. RESPONDENT

Let me begin by asking you a few questions about yourself.

1.01 Sex of respondent.

Select M/F

- 1 – male
- 2 – female

1.02 In what month and year were you born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

1.03 Were you born in **[the country]**?

- 1 – yes ↓
- 2 – no ↓

1.04 a. In which municipality in **[the country]** were you born?

Place of birth (municipality)

1.04. b. In which country were you born?

Country of birth _____

1.05 In what month and year did you first start living permanently in **[the country]**?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

1.06 Which of the items on the card best describes what you are mainly doing at present?

Show Card 1.06: Activity.

- 1 – student, in school, in vocational training
- 2 – employed
- 3 – self-employed
- 4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm
- 5 – unemployed
- 6 – retired
- 7 – in military or civil service
- 8 – homemaker
- 9 – on maternity leave
- 10 – on parental leave or childcare leave
- 11 – ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
- 12 – other status

Education

Now I would like to ask a few questions about your education.

1.07 What is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

[Country-specific list to be compatible with ISCED 11]

ISCED 11 _____

1.08 In what month and year did you reach that level?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

1.09 Have you been enrolled in a formal education program over the last 12 months?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no

Dwelling Unit

Now I would like to ask you some questions about your accommodation.

1.10 How many rooms are there in the dwelling where you live, NOT counting kitchens, bathrooms and toilets? Exclude also rooms used solely for business, hallways and utility rooms.

Number of rooms _____

2. PARTNERSHIPS

Current Partner or Spouse

2.01 Do you have a partner at the moment, that is to say someone with whom you have had a relationship for at least 3 months?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to instructions before 2.41**

2.02 In what month and year was your partner/spouse born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

2.03 Is your partner male or female.

1 – male

2 – female

2.04 a. Was your partner/spouse born in **[the country]**?

1 – yes → **go to 2.05**

2 – no ↓

b. In which country was he/she born?

Country of birth _____

c. In what month and year did he/she first start living permanently in **[the country]**?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

2.05 What is the highest level of education your partner/spouse has successfully completed?
[Country-specific list to be compatible with ISCED 11]

ISCED 11 _____

2.06 Which of the items on the card best describes what he/she is mainly doing at present?

Show Card 1.06: Activity

1 – student, in school, in vocational training

2 – employed

3 – self-employed

4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm

5 – unemployed

6 – retired

7 – in military or civil service

8 – homemaker

9 – on maternity leave

10 – on parental leave or childcare leave

11 – ill or disabled for a long time or permanently

12 – other status

2.07 Is your partner/spouse limited in the ability to undertake normal everyday activities, because of a physical or mental health problem or a disability?

1 – yes

2 – no

2.08 a. Are you and your partner legally married?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 2.09**

b. In what month and year did you marry?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Go to 2.10

2.09 a. Are you and your partner living in a registered partnership?

Note: this question should be adjusted to the formulation suitable in different countries.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 2.10**

Partnerships

b. In what month and year did you register your partnership?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

2.10 a. Does your partner live with you in the same household?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to Routing check before 2.11**

b. In what month and year did you and he/she first start living together?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Routing Instruction: If R is married use 'spouse' and if R is not married use 'partner' wherever 'partner/spouse' is printed.

Current Non-Resident Partner or Spouse

Routing Check: Does R live together with a partner? See 2.10

no → continue ↓

yes → go to 2.17

Note: Rs who have a co-resident partner do not have to answer to this section.

2.11 In what month and year did this relationship start?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

2.12 a. Are you living apart because you and/or your partner want to or because circumstances prevent you from living together? Please choose your answer from the card.

Show Card 2.12a.

1 – I want to live apart

↓

b

2 – both my partner and I want to live apart

↓

b → c

3 – my partner wants to live apart

↓

c

4 – we are constrained by circumstances

↓

d

b. Why do you (R) want to live apart? Please choose the most important reason.

Show Card 2.12b.

- 1 – for financial reasons
- 2 – to keep independence
- 3 – because of children
- 4 – not yet ready for living together
- 5 – other

If 2.12a=2 continue with 2.12c →

If 2.12a=1 continue with 2.13 ↓

c. Why does your partner want to live apart? Please choose the most important reason.

Show Card 2.12c.

- 1 – for financial reasons
- 2 – to keep independence
- 3 – because of children
- 4 – not yet ready for living together
- 5 – other
- 97 – do not know

d. By which circumstances? Please choose the most important circumstances.

Show Card 2.12d.

- 1 – work circumstances
- 2 – financial circumstances
- 3 – housing circumstances
- 4 – legal circumstances
- 5 – my partner has another family
- 6 – other

Routing Check: Is R currently married to P?

yes → go to 2.15

no → continue ↓

[Comment: Countries where it is possible to register a same sex partnership, should route same-sex partners into questions analogous to 2.13, using the appropriate terminology.]

2.13 Have you ever been legally married to him/her?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 2.15**

2.14 In what month and year did you get a divorce?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Partnerships

2.23 To help me to keep track, please tell me the names of all these children, starting with the oldest.

Write in.

name: _____

2.24 a. Sometimes it happens that one loses a child. Are all these children alive?

- 1 – yes..... → **go to 2.25**
- 2 – no

b. Please mention those children who are not alive any more.

Write in.

name: _____

Routing Instruction: Use past tense when asking about a deceased child.

2.25 **Record** the child type – mark the type of child

Instruction: CAI – automatically code the answer based on the location of posed question
Interviewer – Do not pose the question to the respondent – mark based on when the respondent mentions the child

- 1 – biological
- 2 – adopted
- 3 – step

2.26 Now I would like to ask a few questions about each of these children. Is **[name]** male or female?

- 1 – male
- 2 – female

2.27 In what month and year was he/she born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Routing check: Is the child deceased? See 2.24

yes ↓ no → go to 2.29

2.28 In what month and year did he/she die?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Routing check: go to 2.25 for next child. If no more children go to 2.37

2.29 Is **[name]** currently living in the same household with you?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no → **go to routing check before 2.32**
- 3 – some of the time

Routing check: Is the child older than 14? See 2.27

yes ↓ no → go to 2.31

2.30 Which of the items on the card best describes what **[name]** is mainly doing at present?

Show Card 1.06: Activity

- 1 – student, in school, in vocational training
- 2 – employed
- 3 – self-employed
- 4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm
- 5 – unemployed
- 6 – retired
- 7 – in military or civil service
- 8 – homemaker
- 9 – on maternity leave
- 10 – on parental leave or childcare leave
- 11 – ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
- 12 – other status

2.31 Is **[name]** limited in his/her ability to undertake normal everyday activities, because of a physical or mental health problem or a disability?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no

Go to 2.36

Partnerships

I would like to ask a few questions about each of your previous partners or spouses. If you have lived with the same partner/spouse more than once, this counts as separate partnerships. Let us start with your first partnership

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
2.43	To help me to keep track, please tell me the names of all your partners, starting with the first one. Write in.	Name ...							
2.44	In what month and year did you start living together with your first/second/... partner or spouse?	month ... year ...	 						
2.45	a. Were you and he/she legally married?	1 – yes 2 – no → go to 2.46							
	b. In what month and year did you legally marry him/her?	month ... year ...	 						
2.46	In what month and year was he/she born?	month ... year ...	 						
2.47	Have you and [P name] had children together? Please consider only the children of whom you are a biological mother/father.	1 – yes 2 – no → go to 2.64							
2.48	How many biological children have you had together?	number 0 – none → go to 2.64							

Children

		1	2	3	4	5
2.49	To help me to keep track, please tell me the names of all these children, starting with the oldest. Write in.	Name ...				
2.50	a. Sometimes it happens that one loses a child. Are all the children you have with [P name] alive? b. Please mention those children who are not alive any more.	1 – yes 2 – no ↓ tick mark deceased children				

Partnerships

2.75 Based on the information you have provided **[and not counting your current partner]** you have had **[number of partners]** partner relationships in the past. Is this correct?

1 – yes → **go to 2.76**

2 – no ↓

Instructions: Repeat questions 2.43 to 2.71 for all mentioned partnerships.

2.76 Based on the information you have provided you had **[number of biological children – see 2.51]** biological children, **[number of adopted children – see 2.51]** adopted children and **[number of stepchildren – see 2.51]** stepchildren so far. Is this correct?

1 – yes → **go to routing check before 2.78**

2 – no ↓

_____ biological children

_____ adopted children

_____ stepchildren children

2.77 With which of the mentioned partners have you had these children?

Write names/reference numbers of partners from the table on the line below.

Instructions: Repeat questions 2.49 to 2.63 for all mentioned children. Record the number of partnership (2.52) based on the references provided above. Ask the respondent whether the mentioned child is a biological, adopted or stepchild (q 2.51).

Intentions of Union Formation

Routing check:

Does R currently have a partner (see 2.01)?

yes
↓

no
↓

Is R currently living with a partner (see 2.10)?

**Continue with
2.78 referring to
'a partner'**

yes
↓

**Is R currently married to that
partner (see 2.08)?**

yes
↓

go to 2.87

no
↓

go to 2.83

no
↓

**Is R currently married to that partner
(see 2.08)?**

yes
↓

**Continue with
2.78 referring to
'your spouse'**

no
↓

**Continue with 2.78
referring to 'your
partner'**

2.78 Do you intend to start living with a/your partner during the next 3 years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Routing Check: Is R currently married? See 2.08

yes → go to routing check before 2.80

no → ↓

Does R intend to start living together with a partner? see 2.78=3, 4, 5

no → go to routing check before 2.80

yes → ↓

2.79 Do you intend to cohabit or marry straight away?

- 1 – cohabit only
- 2 – marry straight away
- 3 – cohabit at first, marry later

Routing Check: Did R answer 2.78 1 or 2 or "unsure"?

yes → read introductory text ↓

no → go to 2.80

Even though you might not intend to start living together with a partner, we would still like you to reflect on this possibility.

2.80 Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to start living with someone/ your partner. I would like you to tell me what effect this would have on various aspects of your life. Please choose your answers from this card.

Show Card 2.80: Better or Worse.

If you were to start living together with a/your partner, do you think this would be better or worse for ...	much better	better	neither better nor worse	worse	much worse
a. the possibility to do what you want	1	2	3	4	5
b. the amount of money you can spend	1	2	3	4	5
c. the possibility to realize other goals in life	1	2	3	4	5
d. the joy and satisfaction you get from life	1	2	3	4	5

2.81 I'm going to read out some statements about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before people start to live with a partner. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	dis-agree	strongly dis-agree
a. I will be able to financially afford to start living with a/my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
b. I will have access to suitable housing to allow me to start living with a/my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
c. I will be healthy enough to start living with a/my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
d. I will feel ready to start living with a/my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5

2.82 Now, I'm going to read out some statements about what other people might think about you starting to live with a/your partner during the next three years. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Instructions: *Related to item b). At this point we have no information about respondents parents (whether they are alive or not). In case both parents are dead code 99, in case one is alive change the "parents" into "mother" or "father".*

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	dis-agree	strongly dis-agree	my parents are no longer alive
a. Most of my friends think that I should start living together with a/my partner	1	2	3	4	5	
b. My [parents] think that I should start living together with a/my partner	1	2	3	4	5	99
Instructions: If necessary, ask for step-/foster-parents						
Routing check: R has a partner? See 2.01						
yes → ↓ no → go to routing check before 2.83						
c. My partner thinks that we should start living together	1	2	3	4	5	

Routing Check: Is R currently married? See 2.08

yes → go to routing check before 2.87

no → ↓

2.83 Do you intend to marry somebody / your partner during the next 3 years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Routing Check: Is R currently living with the partner? See 2.10

yes → ↓

no → go to routing check before 2.87

Even though you might not intend to marry your partner, we would still like you to reflect on this possibility.

- 2.84 Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to marry your partner. I would like you to tell me what effect this would have on various aspects of your life. Please choose your answers from this card.

Show Card 2.80: Better or Worse.

If you were to marry a/your partner, do you think this would be better or worse for ...	much better	better	neither better nor worse	worse	much worse
a. the possibility to do what you want	1	2	3	4	5
b. the amount of money you can spend	1	2	3	4	5
c. the possibility to realize other goals in life	1	2	3	4	5
d. the joy and satisfaction you get from life	1	2	3	4	5
e. having and raising children	1	2	3	4	5
f. how well you and your partner get along	1	2	3	4	5
g. your legal protection if you would inadvertently experience a break-up	1	2	3	4	5

- 2.85 I'm going to read out some statements about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before people marry. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	dis-agree	strongly dis-agree
a. I will be able to financially afford to marry during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
b. I will have access to suitable housing to allow me to marry my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
c. I will have enough confidence in our relationship to marry my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
d. I will feel ready to marry my partner during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5

- 2.86 Now, I'm going to read out some statements about what other people might think about you marrying your partner during the next three years. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Instructions:

Related to item b). At this point we have no information about respondents parents (whether they are alive or not). In case both parents are dead code 99, in case one is alive change the "parents" into "mother" or "father".

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	dis-agree	strongly dis-agree	my parents are no longer alive
a. Most of my friends think that I should marry my partner	1	2	3	4	5	
b. My [parents] think that I should marry my partner	1	2	3	4	5	99
Instructions: If necessary, ask for step-/foster-parents						
Routing check: R has a partner? See 2.01						
yes → ↓ no → go to routing check before 2.87						

c. My partner thinks that we should marry	1	2	3	4	5	
---	---	---	---	---	---	--

Child Alimony/ Maintenance

Routing Check: *Is any of the R's previous partners still alive (see 2.68)?*

yes → *continue* ↓

no → *go to routing instructions before 2.91*

2.87 Have you received maintenance payments for children at any time over the last 12 months?

- 1 – yes, on a regular basis
- 2 – yes, from time to time
- 3 – no

2.88 Have you paid maintenance payments for children at any time over the last 12 months?

- 1 – yes, on a regular basis
- 2 – yes, from time to time
- 3 – no

Partner Alimony

2.89 Have you received alimony or other payments from (any of) your previous partner(s)/spouse(s) for yourself at any time over the last 12 months?

- 1 – yes, on a regular basis
- 2 – yes, from time to time
- 3 – no

2.90 Have you paid alimony or other payments to (any of) your previous partner(s)/spouse(s) for themselves at any time over the last 12 months?

- 1 – yes, on a regular basis
- 2 – yes, from time to time
- 3 – no

Routing Check: *Does R have any biological or adopted children older than 15 years? See 2.27 and 2.54*

yes → *continue* ↓

no → *go to instructions before 3.01*

Grandchildren

2.91 How many grandchildren do you have?

0 – no grandchildren → *go to instructions before 3.01*

Ask if R has 2 or more grandchildren

Ask if R has 1 grandchild

2.92 a. In what month and year was the oldest of your grandchildren born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

2.93 And in what month and year was the youngest of your grandchildren born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

2.92 b. In what month and year was your grandchild born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Go to routing check before 2.94

Routing Check: *Is the oldest grandchild older than 15 years? See 2.92 a or b*

yes → *continue* ↓

no → *go to instructions before 3.01*

2.94 a. Do you have any great-grandchildren?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to instructions before 3.01**

b. How many?

3. HOUSEHOLD COMPOSITION, ORGANISATION AND PARTNERSHIP QUALITY

Household Composition

Instructions: insert text based on partner/child information – see 2.10, 2.29, 2.56

Now I would like to ask you about all other persons who live in this household. Please count anyone who – when considering the entire year – spends more than an average of two days per week in this household, including those who usually live here but are now away on business, at school, at boarding school, at university, in hospital or somewhere else.

3.01 a. Does anybody else live with you [*live with you and your partner/children*] in this household??

Instructions: Please also consider individuals who are household members only part of the time such as underage children for whom there is a co-parenting arrangement, or young adult children who are students.

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no → go to 3.02

b. How many other people live in your household [*live with you and your partner/children*]?
 _____ other household members

3.02 Please tell me their first names and the initials of their last names [the first name and the initials of the last name of this person].

Name _____

0 – nobody else beside the already mentioned live with R / R lives alone

Household Roster – Other members

#	Temporarily away	Name	Relationship to R	Sex	Age	Month and year of birth	Activity	Disability	Satisfaction
1				M F		M _ _ _ Y _ _ _ _ _ _ _			
2				M F		M _ _ _ Y _ _ _ _ _ _ _			
3				M F		M _ _ _ Y _ _ _ _ _ _ _			
4				M F		M _ _ _ Y _ _ _ _ _ _ _			
5				M F		M _ _ _ Y _ _ _ _ _ _ _			
6				M F		M _ _ _ Y _ _ _ _ _ _ _			

Routing Check: Any other persons living with R? See 3.01

yes → continue ↓ no → go to routing check before 3.11

Now I would like to ask you a few questions about the people who live together with you in this household.

Routing Instruction: Repeat 3.03 - 3.09 for each named household member.

3.03 Does [*name*] usually live here but is now away on business, at school, at boarding school, at university, in hospital or somewhere else?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no → go to 3.03 for next member

3.04 What is **[name]**'s relationship to you?

- 1 – foster child
- 2 – biological or adoptive parent
- 3 – stepparent or foster parent
- 4 – biological or adoptive parent of current partner or spouse
- 5 – stepparent or foster parent of current partner or spouse
- 6 – grand-or great-grandchild (either mine or partner's)
- 7 – grand-or great-grandparent (either mine or partner's)
- 8 – brother or sister
- 9 – my partner's or spouse's brother or sister
- 10 – other relative of mine
- 11 – other relative of my partner or spouse
- 12 – partner or spouse of a child
- 13 – friend
- 14 – acquaintance
- 15 – colleague

Instructions: *Relation is self reported. Interviewer should prompt if necessary.*

Show card: Card 3.04 Relationship to R

3.05 Is **[name]** male or female?

- 1 – male
- 2 – female

3.06 a. In what month and year was he/she born?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__| → **continue with b**
 9997 – Don't know → **go to routing before 3.07**

b. How old is he/she?

Instructions: only ask if date of birth is unknown.

|__|__| years

Routing Instruction: *Is [name] at least 14 years old. See 3.06.*

yes → ↓ **no** → **go to 3.08**

3.07 Which of the items on the card best describes what **[name]** is mainly doing at present?

Show Card 1.06: Activity.

- 1 – student, in school, in vocational training
- 2 – employed
- 3 – self-employed
- 4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm
- 5 – unemployed
- 6 – retired
- 7 – in military or civil service
- 8 – homemaker
- 9 – on maternity leave
- 10 – on parental leave or childcare leave
- 11 – ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
- 12 – other status

3.08 How satisfied are you with your relationship with **[name]**? Please use this card and tell me the value on the scale.

Show Card 1.13: Satisfaction Scale.

Not at all satisfied	Completely satisfied	DK
	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10	97

3.09 a. Is any member of your household limited in his/her ability to carry out normal everyday activities, because of a physical or mental health problem or a disability?

- 1 – yes ↓
- 2 – no → **go to 3.03 for next member or to routing check before 3.11**

b. Who are these persons?

Decision-Making

3.15 We have already talked about the various tasks that have to be done in a household. Now I would like to ask you some questions about decisions. Who makes decisions about the following issues in your household?

Show Card 3.11 and start asking item by item from the table below.

	always me	usually me	me and P about equally	usually P	always P	always or usually someone else	not applicable
a. routine purchases for the household	1	2	3	4	5	6	
b. occasional more expensive purchases for the household	1	2	3	4	5	6	
c. the time you spend in paid work	1	2	3	4	5	6	99
d. the time your partner/spouse spends in paid work	1	2	3	4	5	6	99
e. the way children are raised	1	2	3	4	5	6	99

3.16 How do you and your partner/spouse organise your household income? Which of the items on this card fits best?

Show Card 3.16: Organising income.

- 1 – I manage all the money and give my partner/spouse his/her share → **go to 4.01**
- 2 – my partner/spouse manages all the money and gives me my share .. → **go to 4.01**
- 3 – we pool all the money and each takes out what we need → **go to 4.01**
- 4 – we pool some of the money and keep the rest separate → **go to 4.01**
- 5 – we each keep our own money separate → **continue**
- 6 – other → **go to 4.01**

3.17 How do you manage your monthly expenses that you have together (e.g. rent, food, etc.)?

Show Card 3.17: Organising income II.

- 1 – I pay everything alone
- 2 – my partner pays everything alone
- 3 – we pay both to approximately equal shares
- 4 – we pay both relative to our personal incomes
- 5 – both of us are paying some of them, but there is no fixed rule

4. PARENTS AND PARENTAL HOME

Co-Residence with Biological Parents

Now I would like to ask you some questions about your parents and your parental home.

4.01 ...

Instructions: *Look up from Household Grid and input the correct answer without posing the question to respondent.*

- 1 – living with both of your parents
- 2 – living with your father (not your mother)→ **go to 4.03**
- 3 – living with your mother (not your father)→ **go to 4.04**
- 4 – not living with your parents→ **go to 4.05**

4.02 Are both the parents who are living in this household your biological parents?

- 1 – yes, both.....→ **go to 4.09**
- 2 – no, only my father.....→ **go to 4.05**
- 3 – no, only my mother→ **go to 4.06**
- 4 – no, both are adoptive, foster or step-parents.....→ **go to 4.05**

4.03 Is your father who is living in this household your biological father?

- 1 – yes.....→ **go to 4.05**
- 2 – no→ **go to 4.05**

4.04 Is your mother who is living in this household your biological mother?

- 1 – yes.....→ **go to 4.06**
- 2 – no→ **go to 4.05**

4.05 May I ask you whether your biological mother is still alive?

- 1 – yes, still alive
- 2 – no, not alive any more
- 3 – I do not know whether she is still alive
- 4 – I do not know anything about my biological mother

Flow Check: Is R living with father? see 4.01

no → continue

yes

**Is he R's biological father?
See 4.02 and 4.04**

yes → go to 4.07

no → continue

4.06 May I ask you whether your biological father is still alive?

- 1 – yes, still alive
- 2 – no, not alive any more
- 3 – I do not know whether he is still alive
- 4 – I do not know anything about my biological father

Flow Check: Is R living with none of the parents? see 4.01

yes → continue

no

**Are both of the parents still alive?
See 4.05 and 4.06**

yes → continue

no → go to check before 4.08

4.07 Are your father and mother still living together?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no

Questions about the mother

Routing Check: Is R living with mother? see 4.01

no → continue
↓

yes
↓
Is she R's biological mother?
See 4.02 and 4.04

yes → go to 4.10

no → go to 4.08

Routing check: Is R's mother still alive? see 4.05

no → continue ↓

yes → go to 4.09

DK anything (4) → go to check before 4.24

4.08 In which year did your mother die?

year |__|__|__|__|

4.09 In which year was your mother born?

year |__|__|__|__|

4.10 a. Was your mother born in the [country]?

1 – yes → go to routing check before 4.11

2 – no → continue with b ↓

b. In which country was she born?

Country of birth _____

c. In what year did she first start living permanently in the [country]?

year |__|__|__|__|

Routing Check: Is R's mother still alive? see 4.05

yes → continue

no → go to check before 4.24

Routing Check: Is R living with mother? see 4.01

no → continue
↓

yes
↓
Is she R's biological mother?
See 4.02 and 4.04

yes → go to 4.22

no → continue

Routing Check: Are R's parents living together? see 4.07, 4.01

yes → continue ↓

no → go to 4.14

4.11 Which type of housing do your parents live in?

Show Card 4.11: Parents' type of housing.

1 – living independently

2 – in a dwelling that specifically meets the needs of the elderly (like a service flat, semi-independent sheltered accommodation)→ go to 4.14

3 – in a home for the elderly→ go to 4.14

4 – in a nursing home→ go to 4.14

5 – in a room of a boarding house→ go to 4.14

4.12 Are there other people living with your parents?

1 – yes

2 – no→ go to 4.14

4.13 With whom do they live? Please mention all categories that apply.

Show Card 4.13: Parents' Living Arrangement.

Code all answers that apply.

1 – with their son(s)

2 – with their daughter(s)

3 – with another relative

4 – with a friend

4.14 How long does it take to get from your home to where your parents are living at present?

_____ hours _____ minutes

4.15 Do you intend to start living together with your parents within the next 3 years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

go to 4.21

4.16 Which type of housing does your mother live in?

Show Card 4.11: Parents' type of housing.

- 1 – living independently
- 2 – in a dwelling that specifically meets the needs of the elderly (like a service flat, semi-independent sheltered accommodation)→ **go to 4.19**
- 3 – in a home for the elderly→ **go to 4.19**
- 4 – in a nursing home→ **go to 4.19**
- 5 – in a room of a boarding house→ **go to 4.19**

4.17 Are there other people living with your mother?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no→ **go to 4.19**

4.18 With whom does she live? Please mention all categories that apply.

Show Card 4.13: Parents' Living Arrangement.

Code all answers that apply.

- 1 – with their son(s)
- 2 – with their daughter(s)
- 3 – with another relative
- 4 – with a friend

4.19 How long does it take to get from your home to where your mother is living at present?

_____ hours _____ minutes

4.20 Do you intend to start living together with your mother within the next 3 years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

4.21 How often do you see your mother?

_____ times per: W M Y

0 – never

4.22 How satisfied are you with the relationship with your mother? Please use this card and tell me the value on the scale.

Show Card 1.13: Satisfaction Scale.

Not at all satisfied		Completely satisfied	DK
	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10		97

4.23 Is your mother limited in her ability to carry out normal everyday activities because of a physical or mental health problem or a disability?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no

Questions about the father

Routing Check: Is R living with father? see 4.01

no → continue
↓

yes
↓
Is he R's biological father?
See 4.02 and 4.04

yes → go to 4.10 no → continue

Routing check: Is R's father still alive? see 4.06

no → continue ↓

yes → go to 4.25

DK anything (4) → go to 4.37

4.24 In which year did your father die?

year |__|__|__|__|

4.25 In which year was your father born?

year |__|__|__|__|

4.26 a. Was your father born in the [country]?

1 – yes → **go to routing check before 4.27** 2 – no → continue with b ↓

b. In which country was he born?

Country of birth _____

c. In what year did he first start living permanently in the [country]?

year |__|__|__|__|

Routing Check: Is R's father still alive? see 4.06

yes → continue

no → go to check before 4.35

Routing Check: Is R living with father? see 4.01

no → continue
↓

yes
↓
Is he R's biological father?
See 4.02 and 4.04

yes → go to 4.33 no → continue
↓

Routing Check: Are R's parents living together? see 4.01, 4.07

no → continue ↓

yes → go to 4.32

4.27 Which type of housing does your father live in?

Show Card 4.11: Parents' type of housing.

- 1 – living independently
- 2 – in a dwelling that specifically meets the needs of the elderly (like a service flat, semi-independent sheltered accommodation)→ **go to 4.30**
- 3 – in a home for the elderly→ **go to 4.30**
- 4 – in a nursing home→ **go to 4.30**
- 5 – in a room of a boarding house→ **go to 4.30**

4.28 Are there other people living with your father?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no→ **go to 4.30**

4.29 With whom does he live? Please mention all categories that apply.

Show Card 4.13: Parents' Living Arrangement.

Code all answers that apply.

- 1 – with their son(s)
- 2 – with their daughter(s)

Code: ISCED 11 |__|__|__|__|
 97 – does not know
 99 – not applicable

Routing Check: **Did R live with step father at age 15? See for code 3 in 4.41.**
yes → continue ↓ **no → go to routing check before 4.49**

4.47 What was your biological/adoptive father’s occupation when you were 15?

Code: ISCO 08 |__|__|__|__|
 97 – does not know
 99 – not applicable

4.48 What is the highest level of education that your biological/adoptive father has successfully completed?

Code: ISCED 11 |__|__|__|__|
 97 – does not know
 99 – not applicable

Routing Check: **Did R live with step mother at age 15? See for code 4 in 4.41.**
yes → continue ↓ **no → go to routing check before 4.51**

4.49 What was your biological/adoptive mother’s occupation when you were 15?

Code: ISCO 08 |__|__|__|__|
 97 – does not know
 99 – not applicable

4.50 What is the highest level of education that your biological/adoptive mother has successfully completed?

Code: ISCED 11 |__|__|__|__|
 97 – does not know
 99 – not applicable

Routing Check: Does R currently live with at least one parent or is an orphan?

See for codes 1-3 or 10 in 4.01

yes → go to 4.52 **no → continue ↓**

4.51 In what month and year did you for the first time start living separately from your parents for at least three months?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Go to 5.01

4.52 a. Have you ever lived separately from your parents for at least three months?

1 – yes ↓ 2 – no → **go to instructions before 4.53**

b. In what month and year did that happen for the first time?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Intentions to Start Living Separately from Parents

Instructions: **living with both parents (4.01=1)** → **[living with] = “parents”**
 living with father (4.01=2) → **[living with] = “father”**

living with mother (4.01=3) → [living with] = “mother”

4.53 Do you intend to start living separately from your **[living with]** within the next 3 years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Routing check: R intends to start living separately –see 4.53 = 3 or 4 or “unsure”
yes → continue ↓ no → go to routing check before 4.55

4.54 If you start living separately from your **[living with]**, do you expect to start living with a/your partner?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no

Routing Check: Did R answer 4.53 1 or 2 or “unsure”?
yes → read introductory text ↓ no → go to 4.55

Even though you might not intend to start living separately from your parents, we would still like you to reflect on this possibility.

4.55 Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to start living separately from your **[living with]**. I would like you to tell me what effect this would have on various aspects of your life. Please choose your answers from the card.

Show Card 2.80: Better or Worse.

If you were to start living separately from your parents during the next 3 years, do you think this would be better or worse for ...	much better	better	neither better nor worse	worse	much worse
a. the possibility to do what you want	1	2	3	4	5
b. the amount of money you can spend	1	2	3	4	5
c. the possibility to realize other goals in life	1	2	3	4	5
d. the joy and satisfaction you get from life	1	2	3	4	5
e. your sexual life	1	2	3	4	5

4.56 I'm going to read out some statements about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before people start living separately from their **[living with]**. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. I will be able to financially afford to start living separately from my [living with] during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
b. I will have access to suitable housing to allow me to start living separately from my [living with] during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
c. I will be healthy enough to start living separately from my [living with] during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5
d. I will feel ready to start living separately from my [living with] during the next three years.	1	2	3	4	5

4.57 Now I'm going to read out some statements about what other people might think about you starting to live with a/your partner during the next three years. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. Most of my friends think I should live separately from [living with]	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has at least one parent alive? See 4.01 - 4.06 yes → ↓ no → go to routing check before item c					
b. My [living with] think I should live separately from them	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has a partner? See 2.01 yes → ↓ no → go to 5.01					
c. My partner thinks that I should live separately from my [living with]	1	2	3	4	5

5. NETWORK DELINEATION AND SUPPORT

Emotional support (discussing personal matters)

Now, we have some questions on support that you receive from or give to people around you.

- 5.01 From time to time, most people discuss things that are important to them with others. For example, these may include good or bad things that happen to you, problems you are having, or important concerns you may have. Looking back over the last 12 months, who are the people with whom you typically discuss important personal matters? Please give me the name of each of these persons.

Interviewer instruction: If person named is not from the household, prompt for the initial of last name.

The names of R's alters mentioned so far in the questionnaire are displayed on screen. Link the newly named alters to the existing names. Prompt and clarify the link when necessary.

Childcare provision

Routing Check: Does R have children ≤ 14 in the household? See household grid.

no \rightarrow go to 5.09 yes \rightarrow continue \downarrow

Routing Check: Does R currently live only with [children/a child]? See household grid.

yes \rightarrow go to 5.03 no \rightarrow continue \downarrow

- 5.02 In your household, who took care of the [children/child] over the last 12 months? Please give me the name of each of these persons, excluding yourself.

Now let's talk about people who do not live in your household, but who regularly help you with childcare.

- 5.03 Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with childcare from relatives or friends or other people for whom caring for children is not their primary occupation?

Instructions: Consider only people, who do not live in R's household.

1 – yes \downarrow 2 – no \rightarrow go to 5.07

- 5.04 From whom did you receive this help? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

- 5.05 How frequently did [listed person] help to look after your [children/child]?

_____ per W M Y

- 5.06 Was [listed person] paid for the help?

1 – yes
2 – no

- 5.07 a. Do you get regular help with childcare from a day care centre, a nursery or pre-school, an after-school care-centre, a self-organised childcare group, a babysitter, or from some other institutional or paid arrangement?

1 – yes \downarrow 2 – no \rightarrow go to 5.08

- b. Please name all the alternatives from the card that are regularly used.

Show Card 5.07: Professional childcare providers

[Comment: A country-specific list that covers all institutional arrangements. All the arrangements on the card should also be mentioned in the question text.],

- 1 – babysitter (nanny)

- 2 – day care centre
- 3 – nursery or pre-school
- 4 – after-school care-centre
- 5 – self-organised childcare group
- 6 – other institutional arrangement

c. How frequently do you make use of **[mentioned arrangement]**?

Ask 5.07c for each care mode mentioned in 5.07b.

Write in the table.

	tick mark if mentioned	frequency of use			
		W= week; M= month; Y= year			
1 – babysitter (nanny)		_____ times per	W	M	Y
2 – day care centre		_____ times per	W	M	Y
3 – nursery or pre-school		_____ times per	W	M	Y
4 – after-school care-centre		_____ times per	W	M	Y
5 – self-organised childcare group		_____ times per	W	M	Y
6 – other institutional arrangement		_____ times per	W	M	Y

5.08 How much does your household usually pay for childcare, if anything?

_____ € per W M Y

0 – does not pay for childcare

5.09 Over the last 12 months, have you given help with childcare to other people? If the provision of childcare is your job, please consider only the help you have given outside your professional activities.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to routing check before 5.12**

5.10 To whom have you given this help? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

5.11 How frequently did you help to look after the children of **[listed person]**?

Routing instructions: repeat the question for all named alters.

_____ per W M Y

Practical help

Routing Check: Does R currently live alone? See household grid.

yes → go to introduction before 5.13

no → continue ↓

5.12 In your household, who usually did such household tasks as preparing daily meals, vacuum-cleaning the house, doing the laundry, doing small repairs in and around the house, paying bills and keeping financial records over the last 12 months? Please give me the name of each of these persons, excluding yourself.

Now let's talk about people who do not live in your household, but who regularly help you with your household work.

5.13 Over the last 12 months, did you regularly receive help with household tasks such as preparing daily mails, vacuum-cleaning the house, doing the laundry, doing small repairs in and around the house, paying bills and keeping financial records from people for whom these household chores are not their professional job?

Instructions: Consider only people, who do not live in R's household.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.19**

5.14 From whom did you get this help? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

5.15 How frequently did **[listed person]** help you with household chores?

Routing instructions: repeat the question for all named alters.

_____ per W M Y

5.16 Was **[listed person]** paid for the help?

Routing instructions: repeat the question for all named alters.

1 – yes

2 – no

5.17 a. Do you get regular help with household chores by professional persons from the public sector (e.g., home care services, meals on wheels) or from a private organisation?

1 – yes, from the public sector

2 – yes, from a private organization

3 – yes, but do not know the type of organization

4 – no

b. How frequently do you make use of this help?

_____ per W M Y

5.18 How much does your household usually pay for help with household chores?

_____ € per W M Y

0 – does not pay for household help

5.19 During the last 12 months, have you given regular help with household tasks to people who do not live in your household? If taking care of household tasks is your job, please consider only the help you have given outside your professional activities.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.21**

5.20 To whom have you given this help? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

Personal care

5.21 Do you need regular help with personal care such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed, using the toilet?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.30**

Routing Check: Does R currently live alone? See household grid.

yes → go to introduction before 5.24

no → continue ↓

5.22 Over the last 12 months, is there any person inside this household who has helped you regularly with personal care, such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed, using the toilet?

Interviewer instruction: by regularly we mean daily or almost daily during at least three months. We do not want to capture help during short-term sickness of family members. Please do not consider assistance provided by professional persons from the public sector or from a private organisation.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to introduction before 5.24**

5.23 From whom did you receive this assistance? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

Now let's talk about people who do not live in your household, but who regularly help you with personal care.

5.24 Over the last 12 months, is there any person who has helped you regularly with personal care such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed, using the toilet for whom providing such help is not their professional job?

Instructions: Consider only people, who do not live in R's household.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.28**

5.25 From whom did you receive this assistance? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

5.26 How frequently did **[listed person]** help you with personal care?

Routing instructions: repeat the question for all named alters.

_____ per W M Y

5.27 Was **[listed person]** paid for the help?

Routing instructions: repeat the question for all named alters.

1 – yes

2 – no

5.28 Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with personal care from professional persons from the public sector or from a private organisation?

Answers 1 and 2 may both apply.

1 – yes, from the public sector

2 – yes, from a private organisation

3 – yes, but do not know type of organisation

4 – no

b. How frequently do you make use of this help?

_____ per W M Y

5.29 How much do you usually pay for help with personal care?

_____ € per W M Y

0 – does not pay for personal care

5.30 Over the last 12 months, have you given any person inside or outside the household regular help with personal care, such as washing, getting out of bed, or dressing?

Interviewer instruction: by regularly we mean daily or almost daily during at least three months.

We do not want to capture help during short-term sickness of family members. If the provision of personal care is your job, please consider only the help you have given outside your professional activities.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.32**

5.31 To whom have you given this help? Please name the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

Financial support

5.32 Over the last 12 months, have you **[or your] [spouse/partner]** received any goods or money from anyone inside or outside this household? Please consider only gifts of at least 250 € and do not count shared housing or shared food.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.34**

5.33 From whom have you received this support? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

5.34 Over the last 12 months, have you **[or your] [spouse/partner]** given any goods or money to another person? Please consider only gifts of a value of at least 250 € and do not count shared housing or shared food.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.36**

5.35 To whom have you given this support? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

5.36 Have you **[or your] [spouse/partner]** ever received a contribution or inherited money, goods, or property worth more than 5000 euro **[in local currency]**?

Please do not consider major gifts from a group of people such as on the occasion of a wedding, an anniversary, or another festive event.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 5.39**

5.37 In which year did you **[or your] [spouse/partner]** receive the large gift or inheritance?

Year: _____

5.38 From whom did **you [or your] [spouse/partner]** receive this gift or inheritance? Please give me the first name and the initial of the last name of each of these persons.

Name Interpreters

Note: information on household membership is available through the household grid.

Note: information on sex and age for the partner, other household members, parents, co-resident siblings, and non-resident children is collected in the respective sections of the questionnaire.

5.39 Now I would like to learn more about the persons you have listed. Is **[listed person]** male or female?

1 – Male

2 – Female

5.40 How old is **[listed person]** ?

_____ years

0 – **[listed person]** has deceased

5.41 How is **[listed person]** related to you?

Show Card : 5.41

1 – partner or spouse

2 – biological or adoptive child

3 – foster child

4 – biological or adoptive parent

5 – stepparent or foster parent

6 – biological or adoptive parent of current partner or spouse

7 – stepparent or foster parent of current partner or spouse

Network delineation and support

- 8 – grand- or great-grandchild (either mine or partner's)
- 9 – grand- or great-grandparent (either mine or my partner's)
- 10 – brother or sister
- 11 – my partner's or spouse's brother or sister
- 12 – other relative of mine
- 13 – other relative of my partner or spouse
- 14 – partner or spouse of a child
- 15 – friend
- 16 – acquaintance
- 17 – colleague
- 18 – neighbour
- 19 – other relation (please specify) _____

6. FERTILITY

Routing Check: See 1.02 for R's age

Current Pregnancy

Instructions:

- R is a woman (1.01=2)* → [pregnant] = "Are you currently pregnant?"
- R is a man with a F partner (1.01=1 & 2.01=1)* → [pregnant] = "Is your partner/spouse currently pregnant?"
- R is a man without a partner (1.01=1 & 2.01=2) or
R is a man with a M partner* → [pregnant] = "Do you know of any woman who is currently pregnant by you?"

- 6.01 Now I would like to continue with some questions on pregnancies and having children. [pregnant]
- 1 – yes
 - 2 – no→ go to 6.05
 - 3 – maybe, do not know yet→ go to 6.05
- 6.02 In what month and year is the child expected to be born?
- month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|
- 6.03 Just before this pregnancy began, did you yourself intend to have a/another baby at some time?
- 1 – yes
 - 2 – no→ go to 6.05
 - 3 – not sure
- 6.04 Did this pregnancy occur sooner than you wanted, later than you wanted, or at about the right time?
- 1 – sooner
 - 2 – later
 - 3 – about the right time

Go to instructions before 6.17

Fecundity

- 6.05 Some people are not physically able to have children. As far as you know, is it physically possible for you, yourself, to have a/another baby?
- 1 – definitely not
 - 2 – probably not
 - 3 – probably yes → go to Routing Check before 6.08
 - 4 – definitely yes..... → go to Routing Check before 6.08
 - 97– do not know → go to Routing Check before 6.08

6.06 a. Have you been sterilised or have you had an operation that makes it impossible for you to have a child/ more children?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 6.07**

b. In what month and year did this operation occur?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

go to routing check before 6.08

6.07 In what month and year did you find out that you would (probably) not be able to have a child/ more children?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

97 – do not know, cannot say

Routing Check: **Does R currently have a partner (see 2.01)?**
 yes → continue **no → go to routing check before 6.12**
 ↓

6.08 As far as you know, is it physically possible for your current partner/spouse to have a child of his/her own if he/she wanted to?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – probably yes.....→ **go to 6.10**
- 4 – definitely yes→ **go to 6.10**
- 97– do not know.....→ **go to 6.10**

6.09 a. Has your partner/spouse ever been sterilised or had an operation that makes it impossible for him/her to have a child/ more children?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 6.10**

b. In what month and year did this operation occur?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

6.10 Are you (or your current partner/spouse) doing any of the things listed on this card to help you (your partner/spouse) get pregnant? Please name all of the things you are doing.

Show Card 6.10: Infertility Treatment.

- 1 – receiving medication
- 2 – methods for ascertaining timing of ovulation
- 3 – in vitro fertilisation (IVF) or micro-fertilisation (ICSI)
- 4 – surgery
- 5 – artificial insemination
- 6 – other medical treatment

→ **continue with 6.11**

0 – did not use or do anything (not on the card)

→ **go to Routing Check before 6.12**

6.11 In what month and year did you first start doing something to help you (your partner/spouse) get pregnant this time?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

Go to 6.14

Routing Check: Look at answers to 6.05 and 6.08.

Answer to either 6.05 or 6.08 is '1 – definitely not' ..→ go to 6.14

No such answer given→ continue with 6.12↓

6.12 Are you **[for your partner/spouse]** using or doing any of the things listed on this card to prevent pregnancy at this time? Please name all of the things you use or do.

Show Card 6.12: Contraception

- 1 – condom
- 2 – pills
- 3 – intra-uterine device (coil, loop)
- 4 – diaphragm/ cervical cap
- 5 – foam/ cream/ jelly/ suppository
- 6 – injectables (e.g. Depo-Provera)
- 7 – implants (e.g. Norplant)
- 8 – Persona
- 9 – hormonal emergency contraception afterwards (“morning-after pill”)
- 10 – withdrawal
- 11 – safe period method (rhythm)
- 0 – did not use or do anything (not on the card).....

→ go to 6.14

→ continue with 6.13

6.13 In what month and year did you last use or do anything to prevent pregnancy?

month |__|__| year |__|__|__|__|

0 – never used or did anything

Intentions to Have Children

6.14 Do you intend to have a/another child during the next three years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Routing check: Is R woman 50+, man with a female partner 50+ or man 50+ without a partner?

yes → go to 7.01

no → continue ↓

Routing check: Does R want to have a child in the next 3 years? (answer 3 or 4 or “unsure” to either of the previous two questions)

yes → go to instructions before 6.17

no → continue ↓

6.15 Supposing you do not have a/another child during the next three years, do you intend to have any (more) biological, adoptive or foster children at all?

- 1 – definitely not → **go to 6.18**
- 2 – probably not..... → **go to instructions before 6.17**
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Routing check: Is R “unsure”? See 6.15

yes → go to instructions before 6.17

no → ↓

6.16 Would you prefer your first/next child to be a boy or a girl?

- 1 – boy
- 2 – girl
- 3 – it does not matter

Instructions:

R or P is pregnant (6.01=1) → [How many] = “Not counting your current pregnancy, how many more”

R or P is not pregnant (6.01!=1) and R has 1 or more child (see 2.22, 2.38, 2.48, 2.65, 2.74)

→ [How many] = “How many more”

R or P is not pregnant (6.01!=1) and R has no children (see 2.22, 2.38, 2.48, 2.65, 2.74)

→ [How many] = “How many”

6.17 **[How many]** children in total do you intend to have?

_____ children

Routing Check: Is R or P pregnant (6.01=1)?

yes → go to 7.01

no → ↓

Routing Check: Did R answer 6.14 1 or 2 or “unsure”?

yes → read introductory text ↓

no → go to 6.18

Even though you might not intend to have a/another child, we would still want your opinion about this possibility.

6.18 Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to have a/another child. I would like you to tell me what effect you think this would have on various aspects of your life. Please choose your answers from the card.

Show Card 2.80: Better or Worse.

If you were to have a/another child during the next three years, would it be better or worse for ...	much better	better	neither better nor worse	worse	much worse
a. the possibility to do what you want	1	2	3	4	5
b. the amount of money you can spend	1	2	3	4	5
c. the possibility to realize other goals in life	1	2	3	4	5
d. the joy and satisfaction you get from life	1	2	3	4	5
e. your employment opportunities	1	2	3	4	5
f. your partner's employment opportunities	1	2	3	4	5

6.19 I'm going to read out some statements about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before people have a/another child. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. I will be able to financially afford to have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
b. I will have access to suitable housing to allow me to have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
c. I will be healthy enough to have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
d. I will feel ready to have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5

Fertility

e. I will have a suitable partner with whom to have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
f. I will be able to balance my work and family life if I have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R is male? See 1.01 yes → ↓ no → go to item h					
g. My partner will be healthy enough to have a/another child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
h. I will have access to satisfactory childcare if I have a child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
i. I will have access to sufficient parental leave if I have a child during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5

6.20 Now I'm going to read out some statements about what other people might think about you having a/another child during the next 3 years. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.82: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. Most of my friends think I should have a/another child.	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has at least one parent alive? See 4.01 - 4.06 yes → ↓ no → go to item c					
b. My parents think that I should have a/another child.	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has a partner? See 2.01 yes → ↓ no → go to 7.01					
c. My partner thinks that I should have a/another child.	1	2	3	4	5

7. HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

7.01 All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays? Please answer with this card where 0 means 'extremely dissatisfied' and 10 means 'extremely satisfied'.

Show Card 1.13: Satisfaction Scale.

Not at all satisfied Completely satisfied DK

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 97

Health in General

7.02 How is your health in general?

- 1 – very good
- 2 – good
- 3 – fair
- 4 – bad
- 5 – very bad

7.03 Has a doctor ever told you that you had any of the following conditions?

	yes	no
a. a heart condition (e.g., heart attack, myocardial infarction, coronary thrombosis, congestive heart failure)	1	2
b. high blood pressure or hypertension	1	2
c. high cholesterol	1	2
d. diabetes or high blood sugar	1	2
e. chronic lung disease such as chronic bronchitis or emphysema	1	2
f. asthma	1	2
g. other condition, please specify	1	2

Routing instructions: For all mentioned conditions (1) pose a follow-up question, where [item] is the name of the condition mentioned.

7.04 How old were you when [item] was first diagnosed?

_____ years old

7.05 a. Are you limited in your ability to carry out normal everyday activities, because of a physical or mental health problem or a disability?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → go to 7.06

b. Since how long?

- 1 – less than 6 months
- 2 – 6 months to one year
- 3 – 1 year to 5 years
- 4 – 5 years to 10 years
- 5 – 10 years or more
- 6 – since childhood

7.06 Approximately how much do you weigh (in kilograms)?

_____ kg

7.07 Approximately how tall are you (in centimetres)?

_____ cm

- 7.11 I am going to read out six statements about your current experiences. Please indicate for each of them to what extent they have applied to you recently.

Show Card 7.11: Agreement scale

	yes	more or less	no
a. There are plenty of people that I can lean on in case of trouble	1	2	3
b. I experience a general sense of emptiness	1	2	3
c. I miss having people around	1	2	3
d. There are many people that I can count on completely	1	2	3
e. Often, I feel rejected	1	2	3
f. There are enough people that I feel close to	1	2	3

- 7.12 Please tell me how frequently did you experience the following during the previous week.

Show Card 7.12: Frequency

During the past week...	seldom or never	some-times	often	most or all of the time
a. I felt that I could not shake off the blues even with help from my family or friends	1	2	3	4
b. I felt depressed	1	2	3	4
c. I thought my life had been a failure	1	2	3	4
d. I felt fearful	1	2	3	4
e. I felt sad	1	2	3	4

8. RESPONDENT'S ACTIVITY AND INCOME

8.01 Now I would like to ask you some questions about your present work and daily activities. Early in the interview you have told me that you are **[answer to 1.06]**.

Instructions: Look up the answer to 1.06, code it below, and follow the corresponding route to further questions.

- 1 – a student, in school, in vocational training
- 2 – employed
- 3 – self-employed
- 4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm
- 5 – unemployed
- 6 – retired
- 7 – in military or civil service
- 8 – homemaker
- 9 – on maternity leave
- 10 – on parental leave or childcare leave
- 11 – ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
- 12 – other status..... → go to 8.12

Instructions: insert text based on the current activity – see 8.01

if student - 8.01 = 1 → [start your studies, school or vocational training]

if employed, self-employed or helping member - 8.01 = 2, 3 or 4 → [start this job or business]

if unemployed - 8.01 = 5 → [become unemployed]

if retired - 8.01 = 6 → [retire]

if in military or social service - 8.01 = 7 → [start military or social service]

if homemaker - 8.01 = 8 → [become a homemaker]

if on maternity, parental or childcare leave - 8.01 = 9 or 10 → [start this leave]

if ill or disabled - 8.01 = 11 → [become ill or permanently disabled]

8.02 In what month and year did you **[insert custom text]**?

month |__|_| | year |__|_|_|_|_|

Routing check: Is R employed or retired? see 8.01=2, 3, 6

no → continue ↓

yes → go to routing check before 8.06

8.03 During the last 4 weeks, did you seek a job or paid employment?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no, because I have already found a job that will start later
- 3 – no

Retired or homemaker

Routing check: Has R reported to be retired (6) or a homemaker (8) ?

yes → continue ↓

no → go to routing check before 8.06

8.04 How satisfied are you with being **[retired/homemaker]**? Please use this card and tell me the value on the scale.

Show Card 1.13: Satisfaction Scale.

V1	Not at all satisfied	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Completely satisfied	DK 97
----	----------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----	----------------------	----------

8.05 Do you intend to take a job or start a business within the next three years?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Routing check: Did R report any of the following activities?

student (1), unemployed (5), retired (6), military service (7), homemaker (8), ill or disabled (11)

yes → continue ↓ no → go to routing check before 8.13

8.06 Did you have a job or business directly before you **[current activity]**?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no → **go to 8.12**

I would now like to ask a few questions about your previous job or business. If you were engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, I would like you to tell me only about the one in which you spent most of your working hours.

8.07 What was your last occupation? Please describe the principal activity you performed.

Code: ISCO 08 |__|__|__|__|

8.08 Were you ...

- 1 – employed
- 2 – self-employed → **go to 8.10**
- 3 – in vocational training or → **go to 8.11**
- 4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm → **go to 8.11**

8.09 How many employees did you supervise?

Number of employees _____

0 – no supervised employees

go to 8.11

8.10 How many paid employees did you have, including family members who worked for pay?

Number of employees _____

0 – no paid employees

8.11 Why did you stop working in your previous job or business? Please indicate the main reason.

Show Card 8.11: Reason for Stopping Work.

- 1 – laid off (business closure, redundancy, early retirement, dismissal etc.)
- 2 – mandatory retirement
- 3 – end of contract/temporary job
- 4 – sale/closure of own or family business
- 5 – marriage
- 6 – child birth/need to look after children
- 7 – need to look after old, sick, disabled person(s)
- 8 – partner's/spouse's job required move to another place
- 9 – studying
- 10 – military or social service
- 11 – own illness or disability
- 12 – wanted to retire or to live off private means
- 13 – other reason

8.12 Did you do any paid work in the 7 days ending last Sunday, either as an employee or self-employed?

- 1 – yes → **go to 8.17**
- 2 – no → **go to 8.41**

Maternity, parental or childcare leave

Routing check: Is R on maternity, parental or childcare leave ?

yes → continue ↓ no → go to text before 8.17

8.13 Are you on maternity leave, on parental leave or on childcare leave?

- 1 – on maternity leave
- 2 – on parental leave
- 3 – on childcare leave

Respondent's Activity and Income

8.14 Did you do any paid work in the 7 days ending last Sunday, either as an employee or self-employed?

- 1 – yes
- 2 – no

8.15 Do you have the opportunity to resume your work after your maternity/parental/childcare leave has ended?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no

3 – not applicable; did not work prior to this leave ↓

8.16 a. Do you intend to resume your work after your leave has ended?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

b. Do you intend to work after your leave has ended?

- 1 – definitely not
- 2 – probably not
- 3 – unsure
- 4 – probably yes
- 5 – definitely yes

Questions to Those Who Are Working

I would now like to ask a few questions about your current job or business. If you are engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, I would like you to tell me now only about the one in which you spend most of your working hours.

8.17 What is your current occupation? Please describe the principal activity you perform.

Code: ISCO 08 |__|__|__|__|

Routing check: Is R self employed (see 8.01=3)?

no → continue ↓

yes → go to 8.19

8.18 Is your work full-time or part-time?

- 1 – full-time
- 2 – part-time

8.19 How many hours per week do you normally work in this job or business including overtime?

_____ hours per week

- 8.20 Normally, do you ever do any work at home, including using internet for professional purpose, checking e-mails, having professional phone calls?
 1 – yes, twice or more per week
 2 – yes, less than twice per week
 3 – no
- 8.21 a. Normally, do you work for at least 2 hours in the evening or at night between 8 p.m. and 5 a.m.?
 1 – yes, twice or more per week
 2 – yes, less than twice per week
 3 – no → **go to 8.22 a.**
- b. Is this work usually done at home or somewhere else?
 1 – at home
 2 – somewhere else
- 8.22 a. Normally, do you work on Saturdays or Sundays?
 1 – yes, twice or more in the last four weeks
 2 – yes, less than twice in the last four weeks
 3 – no → **go to 8.23**
- b. Is this work usually done at home or somewhere else?
 1 – at home
 2 – somewhere else
- 8.23 Within your regular or normal pattern of work, is it usual for you to work with fixed starting and finishing times?
 1 – yes
 2 – no
- 8.24 Within your regular or normal pattern of work, is it usual for you to work in shifts?
 1 – yes
 2 – no
- 8.25 How satisfied are you with your current job? Please use this card and tell me the value on the scale.

Show Card 1.13: Satisfaction Scale.

Routing check: Is R employed, in training or working without pay? See 8.01=2, 4, 9, 10 or 8.12=1

yes → continue ↓ no → go to 8.32

Questions to employees

- 8.26 Do you supervise or co-ordinate the work of any personnel?
 1 – yes
 2 – no
- 8.27 Is the business or organisation where you work private, public or mixed?
 1 – private
 2 – public
 3 – mixed
- 8.28 Are you entitled to any of the following services or benefits that are either free or subsidised and are paid for by the business or organisation that you work for? *[Comment: Country specific list]*
- | | yes | no |
|---|-----|----|
| a. child-minding or crèche | 1 | 2 |
| b. health care or medical insurance ... | 1 | 2 |
| c. education and training | 1 | 2 |
| d. housing..... | 1 | 2 |

- 8.29 Does your employer allow regular flexible time arrangements for personal reasons, like for adapting to children's schedules?
 1 – yes
 2 – no
- 8.30 Is your current work contract, if you have any, a permanent contract, a fixed-term contract, or a temporary contract?
 1 – permanent
 2 – fixed-term
 3 – temporary
 4 – no written contract
- 8.31 How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement? 'I might lose my job in the next twelve months'
 1 – strongly agree
 2 – agree
 3 – neither agree nor disagree
 4 – disagree
 5 – strongly disagree

Go to 8.33

Questions to the self-employed

- 8.32 How many paid employees do you have, including family members who work for pay?
 Number of employees _____
 0 – no paid employees

Questions to all those who are working

- 8.33 How often has each of the following happened to you during the past three months?

Show Card 8.33 - Frequency

	several times a week	several times a month	once or twice a month	never
a. I have come home from work too tired to do the chores that need to be done	1	2	3	4
b. It has been difficult for me to fulfil my family responsibilities because of the amount of time I spent on my job	1	2	3	4
c. I have arrived at work too tired to function well because of the household work I had done	1	2	3	4
d. I have found it difficult to concentrate at work because of my family responsibilities	1	2	3	4

Routing Check: Is R older than 55 and not retired? See 1.02, 8.01=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12

yes → continue ↓ no → go to 8.39

- 8.34 Will you be required to retire sometime in the next 3 years?
 1 – yes → **go to 8.36** 2 – no ↓

- 8.35 Do you intend to retire in the next 3 years?
 1 – definitely not
 2 – probably not
 3 – unsure
 4 – probably yes
 5 – definitely yes

Routing Check: Did R answer 8.35 1 or 2 or "unsure"?

yes → read introductory text ↓ no → go to 8.36

Even though you might not intend to retire, we would still like you to reflect on this possibility.

8.36 Suppose that during the next 3 years you were to retire. I would like you to tell me what effect you think this would have on various aspects of your life. Please choose your answers from the card.

Show Card 2.80: Better or Worse.

If you were to retire, do you think this would be better or worse for..	much better	better	neither better nor worse	worse	much worse
a. the possibility to do what you want	1	2	3	4	5
b. the amount of money you can spend	1	2	3	4	5
c. the possibility to realize other goals in life	1	2	3	4	5
d. the joy and satisfaction you get from life	1	2	3	4	5
e. spending time with your family	1	2	3	4	5

8.37 I'm going to read out some statements about conditions that might need to be fulfilled before people retire. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. I will be able to financially afford to retire during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
b. I will be able to adjust well to a life without work if I retire during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
c. I will have access to enough information to help me plan for successful retirement during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5
d. I will feel ready to retire during the next 3 years.	1	2	3	4	5

8.38 Now I'm going to read out some statements about what other people might think about you retiring during the next three years. Please tell me to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements, choosing your answer from this card

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. Most of your friends think that you should retire	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has at least one parent alive? See 4.01 - 4.06 yes → ↓ no → go to routing check before item c					
b. Your parents think that you should retire (Interviewer: if necessary, ask for step-/foster-parents)	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has a partner? See 2.01 yes → ↓ no → go to routing check before item d					
c. Your partner thinks that you should retire (Interviewer: if necessary, ask for step-/foster-parents)	1	2	3	4	5
Routing check: R has children that are alive? See 2.21, 2.37, 2.47, 2.64, 2.74 yes → ↓ no → go to routing check before item e					

Respondent's Activity and Income

Income

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
8.41	<p>This list shows different types of income. Please tell me which of these types of income have you personally received during the last 12 months.</p> <p>Record all the received payment types in this row.</p>	<p>Show Card 8.41: Payment Type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – earnings from paid work 2 – retirement pension 3 – widow's or survivor's or war benefit 4 – disability allowance, incapacity or illness benefit 5 – unemployment benefit or job seeker's allowance 6 – social assistance payment 7 – study benefits or a scholarship 8 – maternity leave, parental leave or childcare leave benefit 							
8.42	<p>How many times have you received this [payment type] during the last 12 months?</p>	<p align="center">Number of times</p>							
8.43	<p>What was the average net amount of this payment?</p> <p><u>For payment types 1 and 2:</u> If you are working with an employer, please include also earnings from any overtime you normally did. Please give me the net-amount, that is, the take-home pay.</p>	<p>Write in amount and go to 8.42 for the next payment type.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 97– do not know → continue with 8.44 98– refused → go to 8.42 for the next payment type 							
8.44	<p>Please look at this card and give me the approximate range of the amount you received each time from that [payment type].</p>	<p>Show Card 8.44: Income Range.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – 499 € or less 2 – 500 to 999 € 3 – 1,000 to 1,499 € 4 – 1,500 to 1,999 € 5 – 2,000 to 2,499 € 6 – 2,500 to 2,999 € 7 – 3,000 to 4,999 € 8 – 5,000 € or more 97 – do not know 98 – refused <p>Go to 8.42 for the next payment type received.</p>							

9. PARTNER'S ACTIVITY AND INCOME

Routing check: Does R have a partner? see 2.01

yes → continue ↓

no → go to text before 10.01

9.01 Now I would like to ask you some questions about your partner's/spouse's present work and daily activities. Early in the interview you have told me that your partner/spouse is **[answer to 2.06]**

Instructions: Look up the answer to 2.06, code it below, and follow the corresponding route to further questions.

- 1 – student, in school, in vocational training
- 2 – employed
- 3 – self-employed
- 4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm
- 5 – unemployed
- 6 – retired
- 7 – in military or civil service
- 8 – homemaker
- 9 – on maternity leave
- 10 – on parental leave or childcare leave
- 11 – ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
- 12 – other status..... → go to 9.09

Instructions: insert text based on the current activity – see 9.01

if student - 9.01 = 1 → [start his/her studies, school or vocational training]

if employed, self-employed or helping member - 9.01 = 2, 3 or 4 → [start this job or business]

if unemployed - 9.01 = 5 → [become unemployed]

if retired - 9.01 = 6 → [retire]

if in military or social service - 9.01 = 7 → [start military or social service]

if homemaker - 9.01 = 8 → [become a homemaker]

if on maternity, parental or childcare leave - 9.01 = 9 or 10 → [start this leave]

if ill or disabled - 9.01 = 11 → [become ill or permanently disabled]

9.02 In what month and year did she/he **[insert custom text]**?

month |__|_| year |__|_|_|_|_|

Routing check: Did R report any of the following activities?

student (1), unemployed (5), retired (6), military service (7), homemaker (8), ill or disabled

(11)

yes → continue ↓

no → go to routing check before 9.10

9.03 Did your partner/spouse have a job or business directly before he/she became **[current status]**?

1 – yes

2 – no → go to 9.09

I would now like to ask a few questions about your partner's/spouse's previous job or business. If he/she was engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, I would like you to tell me only about the one in which he/she spent most of his/her working hours.

9.04 What was his/her last occupation? Please describe the principal activity he/she performed.

Code: ISCO 08 |__|_|_|_|_|

9.05 Was your partner ...

1 – employed,

2 – self-employed → go to 9.07

3 – in vocational training or → go to 9.08

4 – helping family member in a family business or a farm → go to 9.08

Partner's Activity and Income

9.06 How many employees did your partner/spouse supervise?

Number of employees _____

0 – no supervised employees

go to 9.08

9.07 How many paid employees did your partner have, including family members who worked for pay?

Number of employees _____

0 – no paid employees

9.08 Why did your partner/spouse stop working in his/her previous job or business? Please indicate the main reason.

Card 9.08: Reason for Partner Stopping Work

1 – laid off (business closure, redundancy, early retirement, dismissal etc.)

2 – mandatory retirement

3 – end of contract/temporary job

4 – sale/closure of own or family business

5 – marriage

6 – child birth/need to look after children

7 – need to look after old, sick, disabled person(s)

8 – R's job required move to another place

9 – studying

10 – military or social service

11 – own illness or disability

12 – wanted to retire or to live off private means

13 – other reason

9.09 Did your partner/spouse do any paid work in the 7 days ending last Sunday, either as an employee or self-employed?

1 – yes → **go to 9.14**

2 – no → **go to 9.29**

Maternity, parental, childcare leave

Routing check: Is P on maternity, parental or childcare leave ?

yes → continue ↓

no → go to text before 9.14

9.10 Is your partner/spouse on maternity leave, on parental leave or on childcare leave?

1 – on maternity leave

2 – on parental leave

3 – on childcare leave

[Comment: 9.11a and b are meant to be used interchangeably. Version a is to be used in countries where there are no legal provisions for a part-time leave. Version b is to be used in countries where such provisions exist.]

9.11 Did your partner/spouse do any paid work in the 7 days ending last Sunday, either as an employee or self-employed?

1 – yes

2 – no

Partner's Activity and Income

9.12 Does your partner/spouse have the opportunity to resume work after his/her maternity/parental/childcare leave has ended?

1 – yes ↓

2 – no

3 – not applicable; did not work prior to this leave ↓

9.13 a. Does your partner/spouse want to resume work after his/her leave has ended?

1 – yes

2 – no

3 – partner is not sure

97– R does not know

9.13. b. Would your partner/spouse like to resume/start work after his/her leave has ended?

1 – yes

2 – no

3 – partner is not sure

97– R does not know

Questions to Those Whose Partner Is Working

I would now like to ask a few questions about your partner's/spouse's current job or business. If he/she is engaged in two or more jobs or businesses, I would like you to tell me now only about the one in which he/she spends most of his/her working hours.

9.14 What is your partner's/spouse's current occupation? Please describe the principal activity he/she performs.

Code: ISCO 08 |__|__|__|__|

97 – do not know about partner's work → **go to 9.29**

Routing check: Is P self employed (see 9.01=3)?

no → continue ↓

yes → go to 9.16

9.15 Does your partner work full-time or part-time?

1 – full-time

2 – part-time

9.16 How many hours per week does your partner normally work in this job or business including overtime?

_____ hours per week

Partner's Activity and Income

- 9.17 Normally, does your partner ever do any work at home, including using internet for professional purpose, checking e-mails, having professional phone calls?
1 – yes, twice or more per week
2 – yes, less than twice per week
3 – no
- 9.18 a. Normally, does your work for at least 2 hours in the evening or at night between 8 p.m. and 5 a.m.?
1 – yes, twice or more per week
2 – yes, less than twice per week
3 – no → **go to 9.19 a.**
- b. Is this work usually done at home or somewhere else?
1 – at home
2 – somewhere else
- 9.19 a. Normally, does your partner work on Saturdays or Sundays?
1 – yes, twice or more in the last four weeks
2 – yes, less than twice in the last four weeks
3 – no → **go to 9.20**
- b. Is this work usually done at home or somewhere else?
1 – at home
2 – somewhere else
- 9.20 Within his/her regular or normal pattern of work, is it usual for your partner to work with fixed starting and finishing times?
1 – yes
2 – no
- 9.21 Within his/her regular or normal pattern of work, is it usual for your partner to work in shifts?
1 – yes
2 – no

Routing check: Is P employed, in training or working without pay? see 9.01=2, 4, 9, 10 or 9.09=1
yes → continue ↓ no → go to 9.26

Questions to those whose partner is an employee

- 9.22 Does your partner/spouse supervise or co-ordinate the work of any personnel?
1 – yes
2 – no
- 9.23 Is the business or organisation where your partner/spouse works private, public or mixed?
1 – private
2 – public
3 – mixed
- 9.24 Is your partner/spouse entitled to any of the following services or benefits that are either free or subsidised and are paid for by the business or organisation that he/she works for?
- | | yes | no | do not know |
|---|-----|----|-------------|
| a. child-minding or crèche | 1 | 2 | 97 |
| b. health care or medical insurance ... | 1 | 2 | 97 |
| c. education and training | 1 | 2 | 97 |
| d. housing..... | 1 | 2 | 97 |
- 9.25 Does your partner's/spouse's employer allow regular flexible time arrangements for personal reasons, like for adapting to children's schedules?
1 – yes
2 – no
97 – do not know

Go to 9.27

Partner's Activity and Income

Question to those whose partner is self-employed

9.26 How many paid employees does your partner's/spouse's business have, including family members who work for pay?

Number of employees _____

0 – no paid employees

Partner's Additional Job or Business

Routing Check: *Is P on maternity, parental or childcare leave and did not do any paid work in the last 7 days? See 9.11=2*

no → ↓

yes → **go to 9.29**

9.27 Does your partner/spouse currently earn money from an additional job or business? This includes any kind of work like part-time work, odd jobs, homework, second jobs, part-time self-employment, running a small business, or part-time agriculture.

1 – yes ↓

2 – no → **go to 9.29**

9.28 How many hours per week does your partner/spouse normally work in his/her additional job or business including overtime?

Partner's Activity and Income

Partner's Income

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9.29	<p>This list shows different types of income. Please tell me which of these types of income has your partner/spouse personally received during the last 12 months.</p> <p>Record all the received payment types in this row.</p>	<p>Show Card 8.41: Payment Type</p> <p>1 – earnings from paid work 2 – retirement pension 3 – widow's or survivor's or war benefit 4 – disability allowance, incapacity or illness benefit 5 – unemployment benefit or job seeker's allowance 6 – social assistance payment 7 – study benefits or a scholarship 8 – maternity leave, parental leave or childcare leave benefit</p>							
9.30	<p>How many times has your partner/spouse received this [payment type] during the last 12 months?</p>	<p>Number of times</p>							
9.31	<p>What was the average net amount of this payment?</p> <p><u>For payment types 1 and 2:</u> If your partner/spouse is working with an employer, please include also earnings from any overtime he/she normally did. Please give me the net-amount, that is, the take-home pay.</p>	<p>Write in amount and go to 9.30 for the next payment type.</p> <p>97– do not know → continue with 9.32 98– refused → go to 9.30 for the next payment type</p>							
9.32	<p>Please look at this card and give me the approximate range of the amount your partner/spouse received each time from that [payment type].</p>	<p>Show Card 8.44: Income Range.</p> <p>1 – 499 € or less 2 – 500 to 999 € 3 – 1,000 to 1,499 € 4 – 1,500 to 1,999 € 5 – 2,000 to 2,499 € 6 – 2,500 to 2,999 € 7 – 3,000 to 4,999 € 8 – 5,000 € or more 97 – do not know, cannot say 98 – refused</p> <p>Go to 9.30 for the next payment type received.</p>							

10. HOUSEHOLD POSSESSIONS, INCOME AND TRANSFERS

Household Possessions and Economic Deprivation

In the following I would like to talk with you about the financial situation of your household – about the things your household possesses and can afford as well as the income and transfers your household receives.

Routing Check: *Is R the owner of the dwelling? See 1.12 a.=1*

yes → ↓

no → go to 10.03

10.01 Taking into account your own dwelling, any secondary homes, ownership of other real estate, including ownership of land – how much would you say they would sell for at today's market price?

_____ €

Routing Check: *Does the household have a mortgage? See 1.12 b.=1*

yes → ↓

no → go to 10.03

10.02 How much does your household still have to pay on any mortgages linked to the property owned mentioned above in total?

_____ €

10.03 Do you or other members of your household have any savings in the following forms?

	yes	no
a. bank accounts, transaction accounts or savings accounts	1	2
b. government or corporate bonds	1	2
c. stocks or shares	1	2
d. individual retirement accounts	1	2

10.04 A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet ...

- 1 – with great difficulty
- 2 – with difficulty
- 3 – with some difficulty
- 4 – fairly easily
- 5 – easily
- 6 – very easily

10.05 There are some things many people cannot afford even if they would like them. Can I just check whether your household can afford these, supposing you wanted them?

	yes	no
a. keeping your home adequately warm	1	2
b. paying for a week's annual holiday away from home	1	2
c. replacing any worn-out furniture	1	2
d. buying new, rather than second-hand clothes	1	2
e. eating meat, chicken or fish every second day	1	2
f. having friends or family for a drink or meal at least once a month	1	2

10.06 Has your household been in arrears at any time during the past 12 months, that is, unable to pay as scheduled any of the following?

	yes	no
a. rent for accommodation	1	2
b. mortgage payments	1	2
c. utility bills, such as for electricity, water, gas	1	2
d. purchase instalments or other loan repayments	1	2

Total Household Income

10.07 If you add up the income from all sources received during the last 12 months, what is your household's total net income from all members including yourself? Please state the net income, which means after deductions for taxes and social security.

Write in.

If R gave the answer per month, probe:

Does this sum describe the average income of your household over the last 12 months? [If not] Please tell me the average value over the last 12 months.

_____ per M Y → **go to 11.01**

97- do not know, cannot say

98- refused→ **go to 11.01**

10.08 Please look at this card and give me the approximate range of the net monthly income of your household.

Show Card 8.44: Income Range.

1 - 499 € or less

2 - 500 to 999 €

3 - 1,000 to 1,499 €

4 - 1,500 to 1,999 €

5 - 2,000 to 2,499 €

6 - 2,500 to 2,999 €

7 - 3,000 to 4,999 €

8 - 5,000 € or more

97- do not know, cannot say

98- refused

Value Orientations and Attitudes

11.05 There are widely varying views on how we should care for people in our society. Please indicate for each of the topics mentioned whether you think (your own opinion) it is mainly the task for society, the family or for both.

Show Card 11.05: Task for Society, the Family or for Both

	mainly a task for society	more a task for society than for the family	a task equally for both society and the family	more a task for the family than for society	mainly a task for the family
a. Care for older persons in need of care at their home	1	2	3	4	5
b. Care for pre-school children	1	2	3	4	5
c. Care for schoolchildren during after-school hours	1	2	3	4	5
d. Financial support for older people who live below subsistence level	1	2	3	4	5
e. Financial support for younger people with children who live below subsistence level	1	2	3	4	5

11.06 To what extent do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements?

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. Grandparents should look after their grandchildren if the parents of these grandchildren are unable to do so	1	2	3	4	5
b. Parents ought to provide financial help for their adult children when the children are having financial difficulties	1	2	3	4	5
c. If their adult children were in need, parents should adjust their own lives in order to help them	1	2	3	4	5

11.07 I am going to read out some statements about who should take care of an elderly parent. I would like you to say to what extent you agree or disagree with them, choosing your answer from the card.

Show Card 2.81: Agreement Scale.

	strongly agree	agree	neither agree nor disagree	disagree	strongly disagree
a. Children should take responsibility for caring for their parents when parents are in need	1	2	3	4	5
b. Children ought to provide financial help for their parents when their parents are having financial difficulties	1	2	3	4	5
c. Children should have their parents to live with them when parents can no longer look after themselves	1	2	3	4	5

Value Orientations and Attitudes

11.13 That's all the questions I have. Thank you very much for your time and patience. You have been a great help. One of the things we are most interested in is how things might change over time, and so we will come back to interview you again. In case you happen to move, is there someone else we could contact who would help us find you?

Name of contact: _____

Relationship to respondent: _____

Telephone number: _____

Interviewer, tick mark here ___ ONLY if respondent says that he/she does not want to be re-contacted.

12. INTERVIEWER OBSERVATIONS

Interviewer Instruction: Fill in the following answers without asking.

12.01 Interview ended at _____ on _____

12.02 Type of dwelling

- 1 – a detached house
- 2 – a semi-detached house
- 3 – an attached row house
- 4 – an apartment/room in a building of less than 4 floors and no elevator
- 5 – an apartment/room in a building of less than 4 floors and with elevator
- 6 – an apartment/room in a building with 4 floors or more and no elevator
- 7 – an apartment/room in a building with 4 floors or more and with elevator
- 8 – a dwelling unit that specifically meets the needs of the elderly (service-flat, semi-independent, sheltered accommodation)
- 9 – a farm
- 10 – an institution (home for the elderly, nursing home)
- 11 – other, specify ...

12.03 Floor on which R lives

Interviewer Instruction: Fill in the Interviewer Report immediately after the interview.

